

MURAKKAB TIPDAGI UCHINCHI TARTIBLI TENGLAMA UCHUN CHEGARAVIY MASALA

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Annotatsiya.

Mazkur maqolada chegaralanmagan sohada uchinchi tartibli tenglama uchun chegaraviy masala qaralgan bo`lib, masalaning yechimining yagonaligi integral energiya usulida, yechimning mavjudligi esa Fredgolmning ikkinchi tur integral tenglamalari nazariyasidan foydalanilgan holda isbotlangan.

Kalit so`zlar.

Yuqori tartibli tenglama, Fredgolm integral tenglamasi, yechimning yagonaligi, yechimning mavjudligi, Grin funksiyasi.

Masalaning qo`yilishi. Ushbu

$$\left(\alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right) \Delta U(x, y) + C(x, y)U(x, y) = 0 \quad (1)$$

tenglamaning

$$D = \{(x, y) : 0 < x < \infty, 0 < y < \infty\}$$

sohada qaraymiz. Bu yerda

$$\Delta = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}, \quad \alpha^2 + \beta^2 \neq 0, \alpha, \beta = const.$$

Tenglamadagi α va β parametrlarning qiymatlariga qarab chegaraviy masalalar qo`yishda bir necha hollar bo`lishi mumkin.

Masala: shunday $U(x, y)$ funksiya topingki:

- 1) (1) tenglamaning regulyar yechimi bo`lsin;
- 2) $\bar{D}$ sohada uzluksiz bo`lsin;
- 3) chegaraviy shartlari qanoatlantirsin:
 - a) $0 < \frac{\beta}{\alpha} < \infty$ bo`lsa;

$$U(x, y)|_{x=0} = \phi_1(y), \quad 0 \leq y < \infty, \quad (2)$$

$$U_x(x, y)|_{x=0} = \phi_2(y), \quad 0 < y < \infty, \quad (3)$$

$$U(x, y)|_{y=0} = \psi_1(x), \quad 0 \leq x < \infty, \quad (4)$$

$$U_y(x, y)|_{y=0} = \psi_2(x), \quad 0 < x < \infty, \quad (5)$$

$$\lim_{R \rightarrow \infty} |\text{grad}U| = a, \quad R^2 = x^2 + y^2, \quad x > 0, y > 0. \quad (6)$$

b) $\alpha = 0, \beta \neq 0$ bo'lsa, (2), (3), (5), (6);

c) $\beta = 0, \alpha \neq 0$ bo'lsa, (2), (3), (4), (6);

d) $-\infty < \frac{\beta}{\alpha} < 0$ bo'lsa, (2), (4), (5), (6).

Bu yerda $\phi_i(y), \psi_i(x)$ ($i = \overline{1, 2}$) – berilgan funksiyalar, $\phi_1(0) = \psi_1(0)$ kelishuv sharti o'rinli.

Berilgan (1) tenglamada

$$\alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial y} = S \quad (7)$$

belgilash kiritsak, tenglama

$$S\Delta U + CU = 0 \quad (1')$$

ko'rinishga keladi.

S operatorning koeffitsientlari o'zgarmas sonlar bo'lgani uchun (1) tenglamani

$$\Delta SU + CU = 0 \quad (1'')$$

ko'rinishda yozish mumkin. Quyidagi ko'rinishdagi $V(x, y)$ funksiyani kiritsak,

$$SU = V \quad (8) \quad u \quad u \quad \text{holda} \quad (1'')$$

tenglama

$$\Delta V + CU = 0 \quad (9)$$

ko'rinishga keladi.

Laplas tenglamasi uchun (2)-(5) chegaraviy shartlardan foydalanib, quyidagi chegaraviy shartlarni olamiz:

$$V(x, y)|_{x=0} = \bar{\phi}(y), \quad V(x, y)|_{y=0} = \bar{\psi}(x) \quad (10)$$

bunda:

$$\bar{\phi}(y) = \alpha \phi_2(y) + \beta \phi_1'(y)$$

$$\bar{\psi}(x) = \alpha \psi_1(x) + \beta \psi_2(x).$$

Masala yechimining yagonaligi. Aniqlik uchun a) holini qaraymiz.

1-teorema. Agar $R \rightarrow \infty$ da

$$1) |C(x, y)| \leq \frac{C_1}{R^\alpha}, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1, \quad C_1 = const;$$

$$2) \alpha C_x + \beta C_y \geq 0, \quad (C_x \geq \frac{\beta}{\alpha} C_y) \in D, \quad (x, y) \in D$$

bo'lsa, u holda (1)-(5) masalaning bittadan ortiq yechimi mavjud emas.

Isbot. Qo'yilgan masala yechimining yagonaligini ko'rsatish uchun bir jinsli masalaning trivial yechimga ega ekanligini ko'rsatish yetarli.

$$\Delta U = 0 \quad (1')$$

$$U(x, y)|_{x=0} = 0, \quad U_x(x, y)|_{x=0} = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$U(x, y)|_{y=0} = 0, \quad U_y(x, y)|_{y=0} = 0 \quad (12)$$

masalani qaraymiz, ya'ni $\psi_i(x) = \phi_i(y) = 0$.

Endi (9)-(10) masala quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi.

$$\Delta V + CU = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$V(x, y)|_{x=0} = 0, \quad V(x, y)|_{y=0} = 0, \quad (13)$$

$$D_R^\varepsilon = \{(x, y): x^2 + y^2 < R^2, x > \varepsilon, y > \varepsilon\},$$

$$\partial D_R = \{(x, y): (x=0) \cup (y=0) \cup \sigma_R\},$$

$$\sigma_R = \{(x, y): x^2 + y^2 = R^2, x > 0, y > 0\}$$

sohani qaraymiz.

(9) ko'rinishidagi Laplas tenglamasini $V(x, y)$ funksiyaga ko'paytirib, D_R^ε soha bo'yicha integral olamiz:

$$\iint_{D_R^\varepsilon} V(V_{xx} + V_{yy} + CU) dx dy = 0. \quad (14)$$

Bir qancha shakl almashtirishlardan so'ng,

$$\iint_{\partial D_R^\varepsilon} [(VV_x)_x + (VV_y)_y] + \frac{\alpha}{2} \int_{\partial D_R} CU^2 dy + \frac{\beta}{2} \int_{\partial D_R} CU^2 dx =$$

$$\iint_{D_R^\varepsilon} [(V_x)^2 + (V_y)^2 + \frac{1}{2}(\alpha C_x + \beta C_y)U^2] dx dy$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz.

Bir jinsli (13) shartdan foydalansak,

$$\int_{\sigma_R} V \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} ds + \frac{\alpha + \beta}{2} \int_{\sigma_R} CU^2 ds = \iint_{D_R^\varepsilon} \left[(V_x)^2 + (V_y)^2 + \frac{1}{2}(\alpha C_x + \beta C_y)U^2 \right] dx dy \quad (15)$$

1-teoremaning 1-shartida $R \rightarrow \infty$ da $\int_{\partial_R} CU^2 ds$ ifoda nolga aylanadi.

Ma'lumki, cheksiz sohada garmonik bo'lgan funksiyalar uchun quyidagi baholar o'rinli: $R \rightarrow \infty$ da

$$|V| \leq C_1, \quad \left| \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} \right| \leq \frac{C_2}{R^\alpha}$$

bu yerda $C_i = const, i = 1, 2$.

Yuqoridagi tengsizliklardan foydalanib, (15) tenglikning o'ng tomoni uchun quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$\left| \int_{\partial_R} V \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} d\partial_R \right| \leq \int_{\partial_R} |V| \left| \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} \right| d\partial_R \leq \frac{CC_1}{R^2} \int_{\partial_R} d\partial_R = \frac{CC_1}{R^2} \frac{\pi R}{2} = \frac{C}{2R} \quad (16)$$

bu yerda $C = \pi C_1 C_2$.

(16) tengsizlikka asosan (15) ifoda ushbu ko'rinishga keladi.

$$\iint_{D_R^\varepsilon} \left[(V_x)^2 + (V_y)^2 + \frac{1}{2}(\alpha C_x + \beta C_y)U^2 \right] dx dy \leq \frac{C}{2R}.$$

Endi $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0, R \rightarrow \infty$ da limitga o'tsak, u holda

$$\iint_{D_R^\varepsilon} \left[(V_x)^2 + (V_y)^2 + \frac{1}{2}(\alpha C_x + \beta C_y)U^2 \right] dx dy = 0 \quad (17)$$

Bu tenglikdan

$$V_x = 0, \quad V_y = 0, \quad (\alpha C_x + \beta C_y)U^2 = 0 \quad (18)$$

natijaga ega bo'lamiz. Bunda quyidagi hollarni qaraymiz:

1-hol) agar $\alpha C_x + \beta C_y \neq 0$ bo'lsa, u holda (17) dan $\bar{D}$ sohada $U = 0$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

2-hol) agar $\alpha C_x + \beta C_y = 0$ bo'lsa, u holda (18) dan $V_x = V_y = 0$ tenglikni olamiz, $V = const$ bo'ladi. Ammo, bir jinsli (13) shartlarga asosan $\bar{D}$ da $V(x; y) = 0$ bo'lishi kelib chiqadi.

Endi

$$V(x; y) = 0$$

ekanligini e'tiborga olib, (8) belgilashga ko'ra

$$\alpha U_x + \beta U_y = 0 \quad (19)$$

tenglamani (11), (12) chegaraviy shartlardan foydalanib yechamiz. Buning uchun quyidagicha almashtirish bajaramiz:

$$\xi = \beta x - \alpha y, \quad \eta = y \quad (20)$$

Bu tenglamani umumiy yechimi

$$U = \omega(\xi)$$

ko`rinishda bo`ladi. Bu yerda $\omega(\xi)$ – noma'lum funksiya yoki $(x; y)$ koordinatalar sistemasida

$$U(x; y) = \omega(\beta x - \alpha y) = \begin{cases} \omega_1(\beta x - \alpha y), & 0 \leq x \leq \frac{\alpha}{\beta} y, \\ \omega_2(\beta x - \alpha y), & \frac{\alpha}{\beta} y \leq x \leq \infty. \end{cases}$$

Ohirgi tenglikni bir jinsli chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimi

$$U(x, y) = 0, \quad (x, y) \in \bar{D}$$

ekanligini ko`rsatish qiyin emas.

Teorema isbotlandi.

Masalani b) va c) hollardagi chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimining yagonaligi ham a) holi kabi isbotlanadi, d) holda esa Laplas tenglamasini $V(x, y)$ funksiyaga emas, balki $xyV(x, y)$ ko`rinishidagi funksiyaga ko`paytirib, D_R soha bo`yicha integrallaymiz:

Masala yechimining mavjudligi.

2-teorema. Agar 1-teorema shartlari bajarilsa va

1) $\phi_1(y), \phi_2(x), \phi_3(y)$ funksiyalar $O(0, 0)$ nuqta atrofida uzluksiz;

2) $|\phi_1'| \leq \frac{C_1}{y^2}, \quad |\phi_3| \leq \frac{C_3}{y^2}, \quad y \rightarrow \infty,$

$|\phi_2| \leq \frac{C_2}{x^2}, \quad x \rightarrow \infty$ shartlarni qanoatlantirsa, u holda (1)-(5) masalaning

yechimi mavjud.

Isbot. Laplas tenglamasini (10) chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimini izlaymiz. Yechimning mavjudligini isbotlash uchun Grin funksiyalari [3] usulidan foydalanamiz.

$$G(z, \tau) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \ln \left| \frac{z^2 - \tau^{-2}}{z^2 - \tau^2} \right|,$$

bu yerda $z = x + iy, \tau = \xi + i\eta$.

Ma'lumki, Grin funksiyasi

$$\Delta G = 0 \quad (19)$$

tenglamani va

$$G|_{\xi=0} = 0, \quad G|_{\eta=0} = 0 \quad (20)$$

shartlarni qanoatlantiradi.

V funksiya (8)-(10) masalaning yechimi bo'lsin. Biror (x, y) nuqtani ε radiusli va markazi (x, y) nuqtada bo'lgan C_ε aylana bilan o'raymiz. Aylanadan tashqaridagi sohani D_R^ε deb belgilaymiz va bu soha uchun Grin formulasini [3] qo'llaymiz.

$$\iint_{D_R^\varepsilon} [G(\Delta V - V\Delta G)] d\xi d\eta + \int_{\partial D_R^\varepsilon} GCU d\xi d\eta = \int \left(G \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} - V \frac{\partial G}{\partial n} \right) ds \quad (21)$$

(21) tenglikni chap tomoni (19), (20) shartlarga asosan

$$\iint_{D_R^\varepsilon} GCU d\xi d\eta$$

ga teng bo'ladi. O'ng tomonida integral chegarasini almashtirib,

$$\int_{OA \cup \sigma_R \cup OB} \left(G \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} - V \frac{\partial G}{\partial n} \right) ds - \int_{C_\varepsilon} \left(G \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} - V \frac{\partial G}{\partial n} \right) ds = \iint_{D_R^\varepsilon} GCU d\xi d\eta \quad (22)$$

ifodani hosil qilamiz. Ohirgi tenglikda chap tomondagi integralni qaraymiz.

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_{OA \cup \sigma_R \cup OB} \left(G \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} - V \frac{\partial G}{\partial n} \right) ds = \int_{OA \cup OB} \left(G \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} - V \frac{\partial G}{\partial n} \right) ds + \\ &+ \int_{\sigma_R} \left(G \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} - V \frac{\partial G}{\partial n} \right) ds = - \int_{AO} V(0, \eta) G_\xi(x, y; 0, \eta) d\eta + \\ &+ \int_{OB} V(\xi, 0) G_\eta(x, y; \xi, 0) d\eta - \int_{\sigma_R} \left(G \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} - V \frac{\partial G}{\partial n} \right) ds = \\ &= \int_0^R G_\xi(x, y; 0, \eta) \phi_2(\eta) d\eta + \int_0^R G_\eta(x, y; \xi, 0) \psi'(\xi) d\xi - \int_{\sigma_R} \left(G \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} - V \frac{\partial G}{\partial n} \right) ds. \end{aligned}$$

Bu ifodada $R \rightarrow \infty$ da limitga o'tsak,

$$I_1 = \int_0^\infty G_\xi(x, y; 0, \eta) \phi_2(\eta) d\eta + \int_0^\infty G_\eta(x, y; \xi, 0) \psi'_1(\xi) d\xi$$

Keyingi C_ε bo'yicha

$$I_2 = \int_{C_\varepsilon} \left(G \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} - V \frac{\partial G}{\partial n} \right) ds$$

integralni hisoblaymiz. Buning uchun Grin funksiyasini quyidagi ko'inishda yozib olamiz:

$$G(z, \tau) = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \ln|z - \tau| + g(x, y; \xi, \eta) = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \ln \sqrt{(x - \xi)^2 + (y - \eta)^2} + \\ + g(x, y; \xi, \eta) = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \ln r + g(x, y; \xi, \eta).$$

U holda

$$I_{21} = \int_{C_\varepsilon} G \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} ds = \int_{C_\varepsilon} \left[-\frac{1}{2\pi} \ln r + g \right] \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} ds = \\ = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{C_\varepsilon} \left[\ln r \cdot \frac{\partial V}{\partial n}(P^*) \cdot 2\pi\varepsilon \right] ds + \int_{C_\varepsilon} g \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} ds.$$

Bu yerda $\frac{\partial V}{\partial n}(P^*) - \frac{\partial V}{\partial n}$ normal hosilaning C_ε aylana ustidagi o'rta qiymati.

Bu ifodada $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ limitga o'tsak,

$$I_{21} = 0.$$

Endi I_{22} integralni qaraymiz:

$$I_{22} = \int_{C_\varepsilon} -V \frac{\partial G}{\partial n} ds = - \int_{C_\varepsilon} V \frac{\partial G}{\partial n} ds = - \int_{C_\varepsilon} V \left(-\frac{1}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{1}{r} + \frac{\partial g}{\partial r} \right) ds = \\ = \frac{1}{2\pi\varepsilon} \int_{C_\varepsilon} V ds - \int_{C_\varepsilon} V \frac{\partial g}{\partial r} ds = \frac{1}{2\pi\varepsilon} V(P^{**}) \cdot 2\pi\varepsilon + \int_{C_\varepsilon} V \frac{\partial g}{\partial r} ds = \\ = V(P^{**}) + \int_{C_\varepsilon} V \frac{\partial g}{\partial r} ds.$$

Bu yerda P^{**} -chiziq ustidagi ixtiyoriy nuqta. So'nggi ifodada $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ da limitga o'tib,

$$I_{22} = V(x, y)$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz. Bularni e'tiborga olsak,

$$I_2 = V(x, y).$$

U holda (8)-(10) masalaning yechimini ifodalovchi quyidagi formulaga kelamiz:

$$V(x, y) = \int_0^\infty G_\xi(x, y; 0, \eta) \phi_2(\eta) d\eta + \int_0^\infty G_\eta(x, y; \xi, 0) \psi_1'(\xi) d\xi - \\ - \iint_{D_R^\varepsilon} G_\xi(x, y; \xi, \eta) C(\xi, \eta) U(\xi, \eta) d\xi d\eta. \quad (23)$$

yoki Grin funksiyasini qo'ysak:

$$V(x, y) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{x}{x^2 + (y - \eta)^2} - \frac{x}{x^2 + (y + \eta)^2} \right) \phi_2(\eta) d\eta - \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{y}{(x - \xi)^2 + y^2} - \frac{y}{(x + \xi)^2 + y^2} \right) \psi_1'(\xi) d\xi - \iint_{D_R^c} GCU d\xi d\eta. \quad (24)$$

Endi bu formulani (6) shartni qanoatlantirishini tekshiramiz.

Xususiyl holda $\alpha = \beta = 1$ bo'lsin. Ushbu integralni qaraylik,

$$I_3 = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{x}{x^2 + (y - \eta)^2} - \frac{x}{x^2 + (y + \eta)^2} \right) \phi_2(\eta) d\eta.$$

teorema shartlaridan foydalanib, ohirgi integralni baholaymiz:

$$\begin{aligned} I_3 &= \frac{1}{\pi} \left| \int_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{x}{x^2 + (y - \eta)^2} - \frac{x}{x^2 + (y + \eta)^2} \right) \phi_2(\eta) d\eta \right| \leq \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\pi} \left| \int_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{x}{x^2 + (y - \eta)^2} - \frac{x}{x^2 + (y + \eta)^2} \right) \phi_2(\eta) \right| \leq \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \left| \frac{x}{x^2 + (y - \eta)^2} - \frac{x}{x^2 + (y + \eta)^2} \right| |\phi_2(\eta)| d\eta \leq \\ &\leq \frac{N_5}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \left(\left| \frac{x}{x^2 + (y - \eta)^2} \right| + \left| \frac{x}{x^2 + (y + \eta)^2} \right| \right) d\eta \leq \\ &\leq \frac{N_5}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{x}{x^2 + (y - \eta)^2} - \frac{x}{x^2 + (y + \eta)^2} \right) = \\ &= \frac{N_5}{\pi} \left[\arctg \left(\frac{y - \eta}{x} \right) + \arctg \left(\frac{y + \eta}{x} \right) \right] \Big|_0^{\infty} = \quad (25) \\ &= \frac{N_5}{\pi} 2 \arctg \frac{y}{x} \leq N_6. \end{aligned}$$

Demak, $|I_3| \leq N_6$, $N_6 = const$ bahoni olamiz. Xuddi shunday

$$I_4 = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{y}{(x - \xi)^2 + y^2} - \frac{y}{(x + \xi)^2 + y^2} \right) \bar{\psi}(\xi) d\xi. \quad (26)$$

(25) integral ham baholanadi. Bu baholardan quyidagini xulosa qilish mumkin:

$$|V(x, y)| \leq N, \quad R \rightarrow \infty, \quad N = \text{const.}$$

Topilgan $V(x, y)$ funksiyadan foydalanib, (8) tenglamani (2),(4) chegaraviy shartlar bilan yechamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right) U(x, y) &= V(x, y) \\ U_x &= \beta U_\xi, \quad U_y = -\alpha U_\xi + U_\eta \\ \beta U U_\eta + C U &= V \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

(18) almashtirsak (8) tenglama quyidagi ko`rinishni oladi:

$$U_\eta = \frac{1}{\beta} V \left(\frac{\xi + \alpha \eta}{\beta}, \eta \right).$$

So`nggi tenglamani (2),(4) shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimi (x, y) koordinatalar sistemasida

$$U(x, y) = \begin{cases} U_1(x, y), & 0 \leq x \leq \frac{\alpha}{\beta} y, \\ U_2(x, y), & \frac{\alpha}{\beta} y \leq x \leq \infty. \end{cases}$$

ko`rinishda bo`ladi, bu yerda

$$U_1(x, y) = \frac{1}{\beta} \int_{y - \frac{\beta}{\alpha} x}^y V \left(x - \frac{\alpha}{\beta} y + \frac{\alpha}{\beta} t, t \right) dt + \phi_1 \left(y - \frac{\beta}{\alpha} x \right), \quad (27)$$

$$U_2(x, y) = \frac{1}{\beta} \int_0^y V \left(x - \frac{\alpha}{\beta} y + \frac{\alpha}{\beta} t, t \right) dt + \psi_1 \left(x - \frac{\alpha}{\beta} y \right).$$

(27) sistemani umumiy holda ushbu ko`rinishda yozib olamiz.

$$U_i(x, y) = \int_a^y V \left(x - \frac{\alpha}{\beta} y + \frac{\alpha}{\beta} t, t \right) dt + \varphi \left(x - \frac{\alpha}{\beta} y + \frac{\alpha}{\beta} t, t; \xi, \eta \right) \quad (28)$$

$$\text{Agar } a = \begin{cases} y - \frac{\beta}{\alpha} x & \text{bo`lsa, } i = 1 \\ 0 & \text{bo`lsa, } i = 2. \end{cases}$$

(28) tenglikni $i=1$ bo`lgan hol uchun qaraymiz.

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_1 = & \frac{1}{\beta} \int_{y-\frac{\beta}{\alpha}x}^y \left[\frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{t}{t^2 + \left(x + \frac{\alpha}{\beta}y + \frac{\alpha}{\beta}t - \xi\right)^2} - \frac{t}{t^2 + \left(x - \frac{\alpha}{\beta}y + \frac{\alpha}{\beta}t + \xi\right)^2} \right) \bar{\psi}(\xi) d\xi \right] dt - \\
 & - \frac{1}{\pi\beta} \int_{y-\frac{\beta}{\alpha}x}^y \left[\int_0^\infty \left(\frac{x - \frac{\alpha}{\beta}y + \frac{\alpha}{\beta}t}{\left(x - \frac{\alpha}{\beta}y + \frac{\alpha}{\beta}t\right)^2 + (t-\eta)^2} - \frac{x - \frac{\alpha}{\beta}y + \frac{\alpha}{\beta}t}{\left(x - \frac{\alpha}{\beta}y + \frac{\alpha}{\beta}t\right)^2 + (t+\eta)^2} \right) \bar{\varphi}(\eta) d\eta \right] dt \\
 + & + \frac{1}{\beta} \int_{y-\frac{\beta}{\alpha}x}^y \left[\iint_D G\left(x - \frac{\alpha}{\beta}y + \frac{\alpha}{\beta}t, t; \xi, \eta\right) C(\xi, \eta) U(\xi, \eta) d\xi d\eta \right] dt + \phi_1\left(y - \frac{\beta}{\alpha}x\right).
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{29}$$

(29) tenglikda integrallarni hisoblash natijasida quyidagi

$$U_i(x, y) + \iint_D K(x, y; \xi, \eta) U(\xi, \eta) d\xi d\eta = F(x, y) \tag{29}$$

ko`rinishdagi tenglamaga kelamiz. Bu yerda

$$K(x, y; \xi, \eta) = C(\xi, \eta) \int_a^y \left(x - \frac{\alpha}{\beta}y + \frac{\alpha}{\beta}t\right) dt \tag{*}$$

(*) ko`rinishdagi integralni hisoblab, ushbu ko`rinishdagi yechimni olamiz:

$$I = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \left(y - \xi - 3\eta + 3x \frac{\alpha}{\beta} - 2y \frac{\alpha^2}{\beta^2} \right) \ln\left((x - \xi)^2 + (y - \eta)^2\right) + \bar{g}$$

bu yerda

$$\bar{g}\left(x - \frac{\alpha}{\beta}y + \frac{\alpha}{\beta}t, t; \xi, \eta\right) = \int_a^y g\left(x - \frac{\alpha}{\beta}y + \frac{\alpha}{\beta}t, t\right) d\xi d\eta + q_0,$$

$$F(x, y) = \int_0^\infty G_\xi(x, y; 0, \eta) \bar{\varphi}(\eta) d\eta + \int_0^\infty G_\eta(x, y; \xi, 0) \bar{\psi}(\xi) d\xi + \phi_1\left(y - \frac{\beta}{\alpha}x\right),$$

$$G_\xi(x, y; 0, \eta) = \frac{\alpha}{2\beta\left(1 + \frac{\alpha^2}{\beta^2}\right)} \ln\left((y - \eta)^2 + x^2\right) \left(y - \frac{\beta}{\alpha}x + \eta\right) + g_1$$

$$G_{\eta}(x, y; \xi, 0) = \frac{1}{2 \left(1 + \frac{\alpha^2}{\beta^2} \right)} \ln \left(y^2 + (x - \xi)^2 \right) + g_2.$$

(29) tenglama Fredholmning ikkinchi tur integral tenglamasi bo`lib, yechimning mavjudligi yagonalik teoremasidan kelib chiqadi.

Mavjudlik teoremasi shartlari bajarilganda $U(x, y)$ funksiya masalada qo`yilgan barcha shartlarni bajaradi.

Teorema isbotlandi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

1. **Джураев Т.Д.** Краевые задачи для уравнения и смешанного и смешанно составного типов. Ташкент. Фан. 1979.-240 с.
2. **Салахитдинов М.С.** Уравнения смешанно-составного типа. Ташкент. Фан.1974.-156с.
3. **Тихонов А.Н., Самарский А.А.** Уравнения математической физики. М. Наука 1977.-736с.
4. **Зикиров О.С., Газиев К.С.** Об одной краевой задаче для уравнения третьего порядка составного типа. Вестник НУУз. 2017, № 2/2, с138.
5. **Зикиров О.С., Рахматов Н.Б.** О разрешимости нелокальной задачи для нагруженного уравнения третьего порядка. Неклассические уравнения математической физики и их приложения. 2022 г. 6-8-октября.
6. **Сагдуллаева М.М.** Об одной нелокальной задаче для уравнения в частных производных третьего порядка. Неклассические уравнения математической физики и их приложения. 2022 г. 6-8-октября.